

Impact of GST on Indian Economy and Agriculture

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Abstract:-

This paper is an analysis of what the impact of GST (Goods and Services Tax) will be on Indian Tax Scenario. Here stated with a brief description of the historical scenario of Indian taxation and its tax structure. Then the need arose for the change in tax structure from traditional to GST model. GST has be detailed discuss in this paper as the background, silent features and the impact of GST in the present tax scenario in India. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a value added tax to be implemented in India, the decision on which is pending. GST is the only indirect tax that directly affects all sectors and sections of our economy.

Keywords: GST,VAT, INPUT CREDIT Prices, Employment, Economy, Cascading effect, Input tax credit, Impact, GDP, Economic change, budgetary revenues.

Introduction

GST the foremost vital tax reform in India supported the notion of "One nation, one market, one tax" is finally here. The only biggest taxation regime has kicked into force, dismantlement all the inter-state barriers with relation to trade. The GST rollout, with one stroke, has regenerate India into a unified market of one.3 billion people. Fundamentally, the \$2.4-trillion economy is creating an effort to revise itself by doing away with the within tariff barriers and subsuming central, state and native taxes into a unified GST. The rollout has revived the hope of India's financial reform program return momentum and widening the economy can the hopes conquer uncertainty would be determined by however our government works towards making GST a "Good and simple tax".

In the Indian economy, the service sector contributes to over fifty fifth. Separate taxation of products and services is neither viable nor fascinating. GST in India had been introduced to scale back the tax burden that is on each firms and customers. In the previous system, there have been multiple taxes accompanying at every stage of the availability chain, without taking credit for taxes paid at previous stages.

As a result, the top price of the merchandise doesn't clearly show the particular price of the merchandise and the way abundant tax was applied. GST integrated most of the taxes into one tax, where the consumers are benefited. This method provides Input Tax credit paid on the purchase of goods and services, which can be offset with the tax to be paid on the supply of goods and services. As a result, this reduces the general value, with the tip customer paying less. GST could be a game-changing reform for the Indian Economy, because it can bring net acceptable value of the goods and services. Thus, implementation of GST can lead industrial profit, a lot of employment opportunities and would primarily cause economic development that may improve value of the country.

Objectives:-

1. To understand the concept of goods and service tax
2. To study impact of Goods and Services Tax on agriculture sector in India
3. To find out short effect of GST on Economy.
4. To find out the Impact of GST in future.

Research Methodology

The Researchers used secondary explorative analysis technique supported past literature from several journals, annual reports, newspapers and magazines covering wide assortment of educational literature on Goods and Services Tax. In this research, researcher has used both the primary and secondary research methods to collect the information.

Impact of Goods and Service Tax (GST)

1) Food Industry:-

The application of GST to food items will have a significant impact on those who are living under subsistence level. But at the same time, a complete exemption for food items would drastically shrink the tax base. Food includes grains and cereals, meat, fish and poultry, milk and dairy products, fruits and vegetables, candy and confectionary, snacks, prepared meals for home consumption, restaurant meals and beverages. Even if the food is within the scope of GST, such sales would largely remain exempt due to small business registration threshold. Given the exemption of food from CENVAT and 4% VAT on food item, the GST under a single rate would lead to a doubling of tax burden on food.

2) Financial Services:-

In most of the countries GST is not charged on the financial services. Example, In New Zealand most of the services covered except financial services as GST. Under the service tax, India has followed the approach of bringing virtually all financial services within the ambit of tax where consideration for them is in the form of an explicit fee. GST also include financial services on the above grounds only.

3) Information Technology enabled services:-

To be in sync with the best International practices, domestic supply of software should also attract G.S.T. on the basis of mode of transaction. Hence if the software is transferred through electronic form, it should be considered as Intellectual Property and regarded as a service. And if the software is transmitted on media or any other tangible property, then it should be treated as goods and subject to G.S.T. 35 According to a FICCI – Technopak Report. Implant of GST will also help in uniform, simplified and single point Taxation and thereby reduced prices.

4) Impact on Small Enterprises:-

There will be three categories of Small Enterprises in the GST regime. Those below threshold need not register for the GST Those between the threshold and composition turnovers will have the option to pay a turnover based tax or opt to join the GST regime Those above threshold limit will need to be within framework of GST Possible downward changes in the threshold in some States consequent to the introduction of GST may result in obligation being created for some dealers. In this case considerable assistance is desired. In respect of Central GST, the position is slightly more complex. Small scale units manufacturing specified goods are allowed exemptions of excise up to Rs. 1.5 Cores. These units may be required to register for payment of GST, may see this as an additional cost.

The Effect Of Gst On The Agricultural Sector

The agricultural sector is the backbone of our country's economy. The agriculture sector contributes significantly to the country's production. In reality, India is the world's second-largest producer of agricultural products. It accounts for approximately 16% of Indian GDP.[3] India transfers a huge quantity of agricultural products like vegetables, fruits, tea, spices, pulses, etc. This benefits the government to a large extent. In 2018-2019, the agricultural sector has contributed approximately 18 percent to the GDP of our country.

One of the major problems in the agricultural sector is that the farmers are unable to get the actual value for their agricultural products. Also, the most challenging issue faced by the agricultural sector is the transportation of agricultural products beyond the state boundaries throughout India. GST has somewhat resolved the issue of transportation. Presently, there is no GST payable on the transportation of agricultural produce. GST is on the verge of providing India with its first National Market for agricultural goods. Prior to the implementation of GST, when trades took place interstate, the crops were subject to various kinds of taxes. Also, it was a necessity to

obtain a license from each of the states where trade was carried on. This stood as a major drawback in the trading of farming products between states. However, after the implementation of GST markets were liberalised for agricultural products.

Farmers and agricultural company's

Dairy farming, poultry farming, and stock breeding are specially kept out of the definition of Agriculture; hence these are liable to be taxed under the GST regime. The mere cutting of wood or grass, gathering of fruit and raising of manmade forest or rearing of seedlings or plants have also been specifically kept out of the definition of Agriculture, therefore these are also liable to the GST.

A 12 % GST is imposed on butter and other fats (i.e., ghee, butter oil, etc.) and oils derived from milk; dairy spreads. Fertilizer which is an important element of agriculture was previously taxed at 6 %. Under the new GST regime, the tax on fertilizers has been reduced to 5 %. A 12 % GST is levied on fertilizer grade phosphoric acid. GST rate of 18% is levied on pesticides. GST also helps in reducing the cost of heavy machinery used for producing agricultural commodities. A GST of 18 percent is levied on the manufacture of tractors. This is beneficial because the manufacturers are now able to claim the Input Tax Credit. The GST rate of 12 percent is applicable to items, like water pumps, milking machines, and self-unloading trailers and is used for agricultural purposes. Therefore, if an agriculturalist buys any of these products, he is liable to pay GST as these products attract GST.

Agri-commodities like vegetables, fruits, milk, wheat, and rice are of 0 % tax. The tax on select milk products were taxed at 2 %VAT but under the GST regime the rate of fresh milk is nil and other products like condensed milk and skimmed milk are taxed at 18 percent and 5 percent respectively. Dry fruits, jellies, paste jam, and juices are charged with 12 percent and 18 percent. These rates are high compared to the 5 % tax earlier.

Positive Impact Of GST On Agricultural Sector

1. Enhanced mechanism of the supply chain Under the GST regime, the levy on the storage of farm products is excluded. This lowered the farmers' tax burden. It has also given farmers a chance to market their products at the best price possible and minimised the inevitable food loss associated with storage.
2. Credit for Input Tax For the tax already charged for each addition, GST provides each dealer with an Input Tax Credit (ITC). In this way a transparent, trouble-free supply chain will be created, which will enable agri-food to travel freely throughout the world.
3. Transport time reduced Farm products can be destroyed and are also affected by the time they are transported. The introduction of GST should

strengthen the farm market, as a single tax rate is now in place, making transportation of farm goods uncomfortable.

4. Tax exemption GST is a levy levied on consumption. It is only collected if, according to the previously placed excess tax, agricultural items are marketed by manufacturers or on the produce of goods.
5. Ease intergovernmental trade in the past; different taxes were levied on the intergovernmental trade of a single commodity. At each stage of their trade permissions and licences for various states, which caused true problems in exchanging goods, became essential. The introduction of GST has also liberalised agricultural commodity marketing and made it possible for agricultural commodities to operate smoothly.

Negative Impact Of GST On Agricultural Sector

1. Doubling of the tax burden Food products such as fish, meat, poultry, milk products, condensed milk, dried fruit, jellies and so on an increase in taxes relative to previous tax rates. As a result, the food sector's workload has doubled.
2. Reverse charge most agribusinesses rent warehouses to small property owners. Such owners would probably stay unaccompanied suppliers. However, GST will be responsible for the leasing of warehouses by storage and storage agency at the reverse cost of 18 percent. In the form of higher costs or storage of products, the tax burden is invariably passed to producers. The costs of farm products are expected to have a direct effect.
3. Increased storage or cold-storage building costs Previously, most facilities for Agri-storage infrastructure building and food grain handling systems were excluded from service tax. GST reduced the number of exemptions. Both factory building and cold storage are also subject to 18 percent GST for farm products. There cannot be an ITC in this regard, because the external availability of storage service is beyond the field of GST.
4. Modern facilities the imports of project machinery to store agricultural goods such as machined handling systems and pallet racking systems under the former indirect tax regime faced a 5% custom duty and were expressly excluded from duties. This exemption was not granted in accordance with GST. Imports of these commodities are currently 18% IGST. That leads to an increase in the cost of imported machinery, which deters modern agri-infrastructure development.

Conclusion

All sectors of economy whether the industry, business including Govt. departments and service

sector shall have to bear impact of GST. All sections of economy viz., big, medium, small scale units, intermediaries, importers, exporters, traders, professionals and consumers shall be directly affected by GST. One of the biggest taxation reforms in India – the Goods and Service Tax (GST) -- is all set to integrate State economies and boost overall growth. GST will create a single, unified Indian market to make the economy stronger. Experts say that GST is likely to improve tax collections and Boost India's economic development by breaking tax barriers between States and integrating India through a uniform tax rate. Under GST, the taxation burden will be divided equitably between manufacturing and services, through a lower tax rate by increasing the tax base and minimizing exemptions.

The agriculture field includes essentially perishable products and, as the supply chain of commodities becomes easier and the movement of goods quicker, it reduces food waste. Both growers and merchants profit from this. The GST has simplified interstate transportation of goods (particularly perishable food). The tax scheme has now been very transparent. A spike in the price of a few farm products was observed owing to a period of time of increase in the inflation rate. After GST introduction, some of the machines used in agriculture were still more expensive. In the long term, GST would support growers and distributors. Agricultural goods can be sold in the same tax scheme by farmers on various markets and in different states.

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